

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/378852194>

"Exploring Phage Therapy as an Alternative Treatment for Helicobacter pylori Infections: A Review of Current Research"

Conference Paper · March 2024

CITATIONS

0

READS

475

3 authors:

Marwa Metwalli

Director of the Kuwait Reachsci HUB (Cambridge University)

8 PUBLICATIONS 11 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Zeliha Selamoglu

Niğde Ömer Halisdemir Üniversitesi

372 PUBLICATIONS 6,102 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Ebrahim Alinia-Ahandani

Guilan University of Medical Sciences

160 PUBLICATIONS 974 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

"Exploring Phage Therapy as an Alternative Treatment for *Helicobacter pylori* Infections: A Review of Current Research"

Marwa Metwalli
Department of Biochemistry
Benha University
Egypt
Bio.marwadel@gmail.com

Zeliha Selamoglu
Medical Biology Department
Nigde Ömer Halisdemir University
Turkey
Zselamoglu@ohu.edu.tr

Ebrahim Alinia-Ahandani
Department of Biochemistry
Payame Noor University
Tehran, Iran
ebi.alinia@gmail.com

Abstract— (*Helicobacter pylori* is a bacterium that can cause a range of gastrointestinal diseases, including gastritis, peptic ulcers, and stomach cancer. Traditional treatments for *H. pylori* infections involve the use of antibiotics, but the increasing prevalence of antibiotic resistance has led to the exploration of alternative therapies, including phage therapy. Phage therapy is a treatment approach that involves the use of bacteriophages, viruses that infect and kill bacteria, to target specific strains of bacteria. In this paper, we review the current understanding of the use of phage therapy in the treatment of *H. pylori* infections. We discuss the methods used for identifying and isolating phages that target *H. pylori* and the testing and validation of phages for their effectiveness *in vitro*. Although phage therapy shows promise as a potential treatment for *H. pylori* infections, further research is needed to evaluate the safety and efficacy of this approach.)

Keywords— (phage therapy, *Helicobacter pylori*, bacterial infections, alternative treatment, antibiotic resistance, bacteriophages)

I. INTRODUCTION

Helicobacter pylori (*H. pylori*) is a gram-negative pathogen that infects more than 50% of the world's population and has a higher prevalence in developing countries, reaching up to 80% compared to industrialized ones. *H. pylori* is known to cause chronic gastritis, peptic ulcer disease, and has been classified as a type I carcinogen since 1994. Additionally, it has been associated with an increased risk of developing gastric cancer, which is the second most common cause of cancer-related death. *H. pylori*-related gastritis has significant effects on gastric physiology, including the impairment of iron absorption and the potential for vitamin B12 deficiency. The infection has also been linked to impaired energy homeostasis, lipid metabolism, and elevated fasting insulin levels and insulin sensitivity[1].

Antibiotic resistance is a significant threat to global health, food security, and development, with the potential to usher in a post-antibiotic era where even minor injuries and common infections can prove fatal. The rapid emergence of antibiotic-resistant bacteria worldwide poses a serious danger to the effectiveness of antibiotics, which have transformed medicine and saved millions of lives. To combat this issue, the World Health Organization has prioritized addressing antibiotic resistance and endorsed a global action plan on antimicrobial resistance, including antibiotic resistance, in 2015. In addition, federal agencies have taken steps to address the issue by developing national action plans and funding research.

However, the antibiotic resistance crisis has been attributed to the pharmaceutical industry's lack of new drug development, which is partly due to reduced economic incentives and challenging regulatory requirements. The treatment of antibiotic-resistant infections can involve a combination of medications, with the specific treatment plan varying based on individual cases [2].

The discovery of penicillin in the 20th century marked a significant milestone in the fight against bacterial infections. However, the emergence of antibiotic resistance due to non-judicious use of antibiotics, the need for high antibiotic doses to penetrate bacterial biofilms, and bacterial evolution have limited the efficacy of current antibiotic-based therapies. This has resulted in the alarming rise of antibiotic-resistant strains of bacteria, which are responsible for numerous global fatalities each year. Furthermore, the difficulty in eradicating bacterial biofilms, which shield bacteria from antibiotics and immune cells, has posed a significant challenge in the treatment of bacterial infections. In light of these challenges, there has been growing interest in exploring alternative therapies, such as bacteriophages, antimicrobial peptides, and antimicrobial enzymes, as potential alternatives or adjuncts to antibiotic therapy. These alternative therapies have shown promise in the treatment of antibiotic-resistant infections and could potentially address some of the limitations of current antibiotic-based therapies [3].

Bacteriophages are viruses that infect and kill bacteria, and they have been used for decades in some countries as a therapy for bacterial infections [4]. Antimicrobial peptides are naturally occurring molecules that can kill bacteria, and they have shown promise in preclinical studies [5]. Antimicrobial enzymes, such as lysozyme and lactoferrin, can also kill bacteria and are being investigated as potential therapies [6]. These alternative therapies have the potential to overcome some of the limitations of antibiotics, such as the development of resistance, and could be used in combination with antibiotics to enhance their effectiveness [4][5]. However, more research is needed to determine their safety and efficacy in humans [4][5][6].

As antibiotic resistance continues to be a threat, the need for alternative treatments has become increasingly urgent. One such alternative is the use of bacteriophages, or phages, which are viruses that can infect and kill specific bacteria. The term "bacteriophage" was introduced by Felix D'Herelle in 1917 to describe a hypothetical viral agent that could rapidly

kill bacteria. Despite attempts to use bacteriophages to treat infections early on, their viral nature was not widely accepted until the 1940s. Although phage therapy raised hopes in the interwar years, it had largely been abandoned in the West by 1945, up until recently, when the crisis of antibiotic resistance caused interest to rise again. Phage therapy has been used as an alternative therapy for bacterial infections in some countries for decades, with documented adoption and survival in the USSR from 1922 to 1955. While more research is needed to assess the safety and efficacy of phage therapy in humans, recent studies have shown promising results in treating antibiotic-resistant infections. Thus, bacteriophages hold the potential to offer a solution to the pressing problem of antibiotic resistance [7]. However, more research is required, phages may offer a potential solution to the growing problem of antibiotic resistance.

II. PHAGE THERAPY

A. Definition and mechanism of action

Phage therapy, a medical treatment that uses bacteriophages to treat bacterial infections, has gained renewed attention in the West due to advances in high-throughput sequencing, metagenomics, genetic engineering, and synthetic biology. Bacteriophages are viruses that infect and kill bacteria by attaching to specific receptors on the surface of bacterial cells and injecting their genetic material into the cell. Once inside, the phage replicates and produces more phages, which eventually cause the bacterial cell to burst and release new phages into the surrounding environment. This process, known as the lytic cycle, results in the destruction of the bacterial cell. Phage therapy aims to use specific phages that target and kill the bacteria causing the infection, while leaving other bacteria and host cells unharmed. Phages can also be engineered to carry genes that enhance their ability to kill bacteria or to target specific bacterial strains. Phage therapy has the potential to treat multidrug-resistant bacterial infections in different patient populations and reduce antibiotic use in agriculture, aquaculture, animal husbandry, and veterinary medicine [8].

The mode of action of lytic phages in phage therapy allows for the consideration of the history of infection and the development of a therapeutic approach that takes into account its particularities. During the adsorption phase, the phage attaches itself to the bacterial membrane in a highly specific manner, meaning that a given phage can generally only attach itself to a given bacterial species, and sometimes only to specific strains of that species. It then injects its genetic material into the bacterium, which will be replicated via bacterial enzymes, which will also synthesize the proteins and lipids needed to form capsids. After assembling the different components to form virions, the bacterium will be lysed, releasing between 50 and 200 new phages, which can attach themselves to new bacteria and start the cycle over again. Phage therapy involves the use of specific phages that target and eliminate specific bacterial strains, leaving other bacteria and host cells unharmed. Thus, it offers a promising alternative to antibiotics for the treatment of bacterial infections, particularly those caused by multidrug-resistant bacteria [9].

B. Advantages and disadvantages of phage therapy

Phage therapy is a potential alternative to traditional antibiotics for the treatment of bacterial infections. One of the main advantages of phages is their high specificity, which

allows them to target only the bacteria they are designed to attack. This makes them potentially effective in treating infections caused by drug-resistant bacteria, which can be difficult to treat with traditional antibiotics. Phages can also replicate within the host, increasing their numbers and effectiveness, and they can be easily isolated and produced in large quantities. Furthermore, phages have unique properties that make them highly competitive as a supplement to chemical antibiotics, and they can be used in a variety of applications, including agriculture and industry [10][11].

Despite these advantages, there are also several disadvantages associated with phage therapy. For example, the cleavage spectrum of bacteriophages is often too narrow, making it difficult for specific phages to have a desired therapeutic effect. Additionally, bacteriophages in the lysogenic state can transmit toxins and antibiotic resistance genes to bacteria, which can be problematic in clinical settings. Furthermore, bacteriophages release bacterial toxins, such as endotoxins, when lysing bacteria, which can worsen bacterial infections. There are also still some controversial issues that need to be resolved before phages can move to the clinical frontline, including ideal phage screening, effective dosage forms, and clinical practice. Lastly, no data from double-blind randomized controlled clinical trials are available, which limits the ability to assess the safety and effectiveness of phage therapy in comparison to traditional antibiotics [10][11].

C. Previous applications of phage therapy in other bacterial infections

According to previous studies, phage therapy has been applied to treat various bacterial infections, including pneumonia, burns, urinary tract infections, atopic dermatitis, implanted prosthetic devices, otitis, and gastrointestinal infections [12]. Personalized phage therapy has also been shown to be effective in treating serious bacterial infections, as highlighted by three seminal case reports conducted under the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) emergency Investigational New Drug (eIND) mechanism [13].

In addition, the use of phage therapy in treating other bacterial infections has been documented. For example, anti-cholera phage has been shown to selectively reduce the majority of vibrios without interfering with other intestinal microorganisms and without any noticeable toxic effect on the patient, as demonstrated in experiments conducted in Pakistan in the 1970s [12]. The use of phage therapy to treat wounds was also documented during World War II in the Soviet Union and Germany. Furthermore, potential use of phage therapy in treating *Clostridium perfringens* infections and as a novel promising antivenom therapy has also been suggested [12] [13].

III. IDENTIFYING AND ISOLATING PHAGES TARGETING H. PYLORI

A. Methods for identifying and isolating phages

There are several techniques for identifying and isolating phages. Despite the fact that more research is required, phages may offer a potential solution to the growing problem of antibiotic resistance. The golden standard for phage enumeration is plaque counting, which involves using the

double agar overlay assay (DLA) to allow localized phage-host contact in a confined environment. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) can also be used to visualize and quantify viral particles, but the sample needs to be highly concentrated. For quantification in complex samples, such as clinical specimens or food, specific treatments are needed due to the presence of chemical compounds that may impact the results. Physical separation should be applied before viral nucleic acid isolation to minimize the carryover of PCR inhibitors. Next-generation sequencing can also be used for enumeration of phages in complex samples, but filtering of reads to remove non-viral sequences is necessary. Overall, selecting the proper pretreatment and downstream methods is important to obtain comprehensive results about phage concentration when dealing with complex samples[14].

B. Criteria for selecting phages targeting *H. pylori*

When selecting phages for targeting *H. pylori*, it is important to consider their specificity, effectiveness, and safety for use in humans. One criterion for selecting phages targeting *H. pylori* involves identifying phages that are highly specific and effective in eliminating *H. pylori*. Additionally, the phages must target the bacteria responsible for the infection and be effective against a broad range of *H. pylori* strains. Finally, the selected phages must not harm other beneficial bacteria in the gut and be safe for use in humans. Studies also suggest that phage therapy is not suitable for polymicrobial infections, emphasizing the importance of identifying phages that are highly specific to *H. pylori*. Therefore, careful consideration of these criteria is necessary when selecting phages for targeting *H. pylori* [15][16][17].

C. Challenges in the identification and isolation of *H. pylori* phages

The use of phages as a promising approach for future therapies against *H. pylori* infection is hindered by the challenges in identifying and isolating *H. pylori* phages. Despite the potential of phage therapy, the understanding of *H. pylori* phage biology is still in its infancy. Studies highlight the need for further research to improve the understanding of phage and *H. pylori* interactions, and to identify more lytic phages of *H. pylori* that can be used for phage therapy. Moreover, the document suggests that the methods used for phage induction in some studies may not be optimal, and other strategies may be more effective in inducing phages. Therefore, addressing these challenges is critical to consider phage therapy as an alternative approach for eradicating *H. pylori*, especially in cases of low eradication rates and antibiotic resistance [19].

IV. TESTING AND VALIDATION OF *H. PYLORI* PHAGES

A. *In vitro* testing of phages

The testing and validation of a new phage, HPy1R, against *H. pylori* in vitro showed promising results. The phage remained stable over a wide range of pH levels and temperatures and was effective in reducing the growth of *H. pylori* in vitro. The study provides evidence for the potential of phage therapy as a treatment for *H. pylori* infections, but further research is needed to evaluate its safety and efficacy in vivo [20][21].

B. The isolation of a new phage and its efficacy

The new phage, HPy1R, was isolated by exposing the clinical *H. pylori* strain 11057A to UV radiation for 60 seconds. The isolation protocol used by the researchers was similar to that reported by Lehours et al. who also used UV light to isolate phages. However, spontaneous induction of phages was also observed in other *H. pylori* strains, as well as induction of prophages after subsequent exposure to citrate-phosphate buffer at pH 6 and 3. The researchers used a panel of 75 random *H. pylori* human clinical isolates from gastric biopsies of Portuguese patients with different gastric diseases and reference strain SS1 to determine the phage lytic range and its relative efficiency of plating. HPy1R displayed a broad spectrum of action, causing visible haloes of inhibition in 78.9% (60/76) of the tested strains (21) (22).

Ferreira et al., describe the isolation and characterization of a new phage, HPy1R, and its efficacy against *H. pylori* in vitro. The phage was isolated from a clinical *H. pylori* strain using UV radiation treatment. The phage was found to have a linear double-stranded DNA molecule of 31,162 bp with 37.1% GC content. The phage genome encodes 36 coding sequences (CDSs), of which 19 could not be functionally assigned, whereas the other 17 were similar to known *H. pylori* phage proteins. The phage was found to be temperate in nature and was confirmed by the detection of integrase in the host genome. The phage was also found to have a broad spectrum of action, causing visible haloes of inhibition in 78.9% of the tested *H. pylori* strains. The phage was effective against *H. pylori* in vitro, and no tRNAs or antibiotic resistance genes were identified in the phage genome. The study suggests that phage therapy may be a potential treatment option for *H. pylori* infections (21).

The efficacy of HPy1R against *H. pylori* was tested in vitro. The results showed that the phage was less effective 6 hours after infection, as no statistical differences in the number of bacterial cells between control and phage-treated cells could be observed. However, HPy1R was able to maintain the *H. pylori* population at low levels for up to 24 hours post-infection, with multiplicities of infection (MOIs) of 0.01, 0.1, and 1. Interestingly, similar growth inhibition in the bacterial cell population was observed using all tested MOIs. The study also explored the gastric behavior of HPy1R using a harmonized static in vitro digestion model comprising oral and gastric phases. The results showed that HPy1R was stable in the 2 minutes of the oral phase, and in the gastric phase, the phage concentration decreased by 2.24 and 2.27 orders of magnitude after 1 and 2 hours, respectively, relative to the control. The study suggests that HPy1R may be a potential treatment option for *H. pylori* infections, and further studies are needed to determine its efficacy in vivo (21)

V. SAFETY AND EFFICACY OF PHAGE THERAPY FOR *H. PYLORI* INFECTIONS

A. Current state of research

The potential of phage therapy as an alternative treatment for *H. pylori* infections, which are becoming increasingly resistant to antibiotics, has been a topic of interest in the current state of research. The results indicate that phages may be a realistic alternative to combat *H. pylori* infections, but additional studies are required to evaluate safety, toxicity, and

the absence of transmission of virulence genes. Studies suggest that genetic engineering and the use of phage cocktails may enhance the efficacy and safety of phages. Despite the promising results, further research is required to fully assess the safety and efficacy of phage therapy as a treatment for *H. pylori* infections [23].

B. Future directions and potential challenges

In the future, more research is needed to address the challenges associated with the use of phage therapy as a treatment for *H. pylori* infections. One of the main challenges is the limited understanding of *H. pylori* phage biology, which hinders the development of effective phage therapy strategies. Further research is also necessary to assess the safety and toxicity of phages, as well as their potential to transmit virulence genes. Additionally, the development of lytic and customized variants of temperate phages, as well as the use of phage cocktails, could broaden the spectrum of action against *H. pylori* infections. In summary, further research is required to fully understand the potential of phage therapy for the treatment of *H. pylori* infections and overcome the challenges associated with its use [23][19].

C. Ethical considerations

ethical considerations should be taken into account when considering the use of phage therapy. These may include issues related to informed consent, patient autonomy, and the potential for unintended consequences or harm. Additionally, the use of phage therapy may raise questions about the regulation and oversight of such treatments, particularly in countries where phage therapy is not yet widely used or regulated. It is important for researchers and healthcare providers to carefully consider these ethical considerations and ensure that patients are fully informed about the potential risks and benefits of phage therapy before undergoing treatment [22][23][24].

VI. CONCLUSION

The overall assessment of phage therapy as an alternative treatment for *H. pylori* infections is promising, but further research and development are needed to fully evaluate its safety and efficacy. While studies suggest that phages may be effective and safe, there are still several challenges that need to be addressed, including limited understanding of *H. pylori* phage biology and the need for further research to assess the safety and toxicity of phages. However, the development of lytic and customized variants of temperate phages, as well as the use of phage cocktails, could help broaden the spectrum of action against *H. pylori* infections. Overall, the potential of phage therapy as a treatment for *H. pylori* infections is significant, but additional research is needed to fully realize its potential and address the challenges associated with its use.

In terms of clinical practice, future research should focus on conducting double-blind randomized controlled clinical trials to provide further evidence of the safety and efficacy of phage therapy compared to traditional antibiotics. This research should also address the challenges associated with identifying and isolating *H. pylori* phages, and aim to develop effective phage therapy strategies that take into account the specificity, effectiveness, and safety of phages for use in humans. Furthermore, regulatory oversight should be considered in countries where phage therapy is not yet widely used or regulated [18][25].

REFERENCES

- [1] H.A. Abd El-Maksoud, K.M. Fararh, and M. Metwaly, "Biochemical changes associated with helicobacter pylori infection," Department of Biochemistry, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Benha, Department of Clinical pathology, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Benha University, Egypt.
- [2] C. L. Ventola, "The antibiotic resistance crisis: part 1: causes and threats," *Pharmacy and therapeutics*, vol. 40, no. 4, pp. 277, 2015.
- [3] P. P. Kalelkar, M. Riddick, and A. J. García, "Biomaterial-based antimicrobial therapies for the treatment of bacterial infections," *Advanced Healthcare Materials*, vol. 9, no. 14, p. 2002106, 2020.
- [4] B. K. Chan, S. T. Abedon, and C. Loc-Carrillo, "Phage cocktails and the future of phage therapy," *Future microbiology*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 769-783, 2013.
- [5] A. A. Bahar and D. Ren, "Antimicrobial peptides," *Pharmaceuticals*, vol. 6, no. 12, pp. 1543-1575, 2013.
- [6] H. C. Flemming et al., "Biofilms: an emergent form of bacterial life," *Nature Reviews Microbiology*, vol. 14, no. 9, pp. 563-575, 2016.
- [7] Myelnikov, D. (2018). An alternative cure: the adoption and survival of bacteriophage therapy in the USSR, 1922–1955. *Journal of the History of Medicine and Allied Sciences*, 73(4), 385-411.
- [8] S. A. Strathdee, G. F. Hatfull, V. K. Mutalik, and R. T. Schooley, "Phage therapy: From biological mechanisms to future directions," *Cell*, vol. 186, no. 1, pp. 17-31, Jun. 2023.
- [9] C. Brives and J. Pourraz, "Phage therapy as a potential solution in the fight against AMR: obstacles and possible futures," *Palgrave Communications*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 1-11, Nov. 2020.
- [10] J. Lin, F. Du, M. Long, and P. Li, "Limitations of phage therapy and corresponding optimization strategies: a review," *Molecules*, vol. 27, no. 6, p. 1857, 2022. doi: 10.3390/molecules27061857
- [11] N.Principi, E. Silvestri, and S. Esposito, "Advantages and limitations of bacteriophages for the treatment of bacterial infections," *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, vol. 10, p. 513, 2019. doi: 10.3389/fphar.2019.00513
- [12] A. A. Cisek, I. Dąbrowska, K. P. Gregorczyk, and Z. Wyżewski, "Phage therapy in bacterial infections treatment: one hundred years after the discovery of bacteriophages," *Current microbiology*, vol. 74, pp. 277-283, 2017.
- [13] G. F. Hatfull, R. M. Dedrick, and R. T. Schooley, "Phage therapy for antibiotic-resistant bacterial infections," *Annual Review of Medicine*, vol. 73, pp. 197-211, Jan. 2022.
- [14] N. Ács, M. Gambino, and L. Brøndsted, "Bacteriophage enumeration and detection methods," *Frontiers in Microbiology*, vol. 11, p. 2662, 2020.
- [15] F. F. Vale, A. P. Matos, P. Carvalho, and J. M. Vítor, "Helicobacter pylori phage screening," *Microscopy and Microanalysis*, vol. 14, no. S3, pp. 150-151, 2008.
- [16] D. R. Harper, "Criteria for selecting suitable infectious diseases for phage therapy," *Viruses*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 177, 2018.
- [17] P. Lehours, F. F. Vale, M. K. Bjursell, O. Melefors, R. Advani, S. Glavas et al., "Genome sequencing reveals a phage in Helicobacter pylori," *MBio*, vol. 2, no. 6, pp. e00239-11, 2011.
- [18] E. Alinia-Ahandani, M. M. Matwalli, S. Hosseinejad, M. Sheydaei, H. Darzi-Ramandi, Z. Alizadeh-Tarpoei, and S. S. Heidary-Bazardehy, "Assessment of the Relation of Anti-TPO and TSH, T3 and T4 Levels between Some Subclinical Diabetes Patients in Iran," *Journal of Pharmaceutical Research International*, vol. 34, no. 31A, pp. 16-25, Apr. 2022.
- [19] A. B. Muñoz, J. Stepanian, A. A. Trespalacios, and F. F. Vale, "Bacteriophages of Helicobacter pylori," *Frontiers in Microbiology*, vol. 11, p. 549084, 2020.
- [20] A. Randel, "H. pylori infection: ACG updates treatment recommendations," *American family physician*, vol. 97, no. 2, pp. 135-137, 2018.
- [21] R. Ferreira, C. Sousa, R. F. Gonçalves, A. C. Pinheiro, M. Oleastro, J. Wagemans, et al., "Characterization and genomic analysis of a new phage infecting Helicobacter pylori," *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, vol. 23, no. 14, p. 7885, 2022.

- [22] P. Lehours, F. F. Vale, M. K. Bjursell, O. Melefors, R. Advani, S. Glavas, et al., "Genome sequencing reveals a phage in *Helicobacter pylori*," *MBio*, vol. 2, no. 6, p. e00239-11, 2011.
- [23] R. Ferreira, C. Sousa, R. F. Gonçalves, A. C. Pinheiro, M. Oleastro, J. Wagemans, et al., "Characterization and genomic analysis of a new phage infecting *Helicobacter pylori*," *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, vol. 23, no. 14, p. 7885, 2022.
- [24] E. Fernandez-Gonzalez and S. Backert, "DNA transfer in the gastric pathogen *Helicobacter pylori*," *Journal of gastroenterology*, vol. 49, pp. 594-604, 2014.
- [25] Z. Selamoglu, S. Hajipour, Q. A. Khan, and E. A. Ahandani, "The Effects on Antiaging Molecules of Physical Exercise," *Bioengineering Studies*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 26-30, Sep. 2022.